

UREA ADDUCTS OF FATTY ACIDS. PART VI. COMPONENT FATTY ACIDS OF COCONUT OIL

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Decreasing solvent crystallisation method and urea adducts elution method have been applied to fractionate methyl esters of coconut oil fatty acids. An attempt has been made to build up the composition of fatty acids in the oil from the saponification equivalents and iodine values of the fractions. Due to the limitations of the effective application of urea fractionation technique to coconut and similar fats, it may be efficiently used to substitute the lead-salt-alcohol method suggested by Hilditch.

Schlenk and Holman¹ have effectively separated long and short chain fatty acids and also saturated and unsaturated acids from a binary mixture by a single dose urea precipitation. They have been able to segregate highly unsaturated fraction from the natural mixture of fatty acids of oils. The separation of oleic acid from various low quality commercial fats by the combined method of solvent crystallisation and urea precipitation has been attempted by Swern and Parker². It is interesting to observe the efficiency and limitations of urea fractionation when applied to coconut oil and similar fats due to their characteristic composition containing lower saturated acids such as myristic, lauric and lower than lauric acids. The present work has been undertaken with a view to studying how the separation of oleic acid from long and short chain saturated acids proceeds in a natural mixture of coconut oil fatty acid esters by successive urea precipitation method. Methyl esters of coconut oil fatty acids are dissolved with sufficient amount of urea in methanol. Alcohol is then decreased stepwise by distillation to obtain different fractions of urea adducts. This method has been referred to as decreasing solvent crystallisation method of urea fractionation by Mehta, Rao and Abhyankar³. In order to segregate the lower saturated fatty acids and oleic acid, urea adducts of all the fatty acid esters are first formed by using excess of urea with least amount of alcohol. The unstable and loosely bound adducts are then separated by dissolving the adduct in limited amount of alcohol. Thus by successive elution, a series of fractions is obtained from the mother-liquors. This technique is termed here as urea adducts elution method.

EXPERIMENTAL

Methyl esters of coconut oil fatty acids were prepared by inter-esterification of oil by the method followed by Bradley and Johnston⁴. To 200 g.

TABLE I

Methyl esters(100 g.) of coconut oil fatty acids (I.V. 6.9; S.E. 224) + 300 g. urea + 2.3 litres of methanol.

Frac- tion No.	Solvent removed, (mL).	Wt. of esters (W g.).	I. V. (I_w).	S. E. (SE_w).	Unsat. esters (u) ^b .	% Unsat. esters in fraction.	Sat. esters. (W-u).	% Sat. esters in fraction.	Mol. ratio of sat./unsat.	Approx. comp. of saturated.				
										C ₁₆ .	C ₁₈ .	C ₂₀ .		
1	Kept overnight	41.92		
1a	200	14.23	0.6	251.6	0.10	0.70	14.13	99.3	158.5	4.89	9.24	...		
1b	300	16.00	3.0	236.8	0.56	3.50	15.44	96.5	33.0	...	1.18	14.26		
1c	Removed completely	11.69	7.4	217.4	1.00	8.60	10.69	91.4	14.1	6.26	4.43	
2	400	10.05	5.7	230.9	0.67	6.67	9.38	93.33	17.4	...	4.64	4.74	...	
3	400	10.41	7.3	223.8	0.89	8.55	9.52	91.45	13.5	...	3.18	6.35	...	
4	300	11.24	8.6	218.2	1.13	10.06	10.11	39.94	11.9	9.42	0.69	
5	300	10.41	9.2	211.9	1.12	10.76	9.29	89.24	11.4	6.49	2.81	
6	300	8.36	8.4	201.5	0.83	9.61	7.53	90.19	13.2	3.00	4.54	
7	Alcohol removed completely	7.59	22.4	198.6	1.99	26.22	5.60	73.78	4.5	4.09	1.51
Total esters		99.98	8.29	...	91.69	4.89	18.24	50.52	16.56	1.51
Total acids		8.3	...	91.7	4.9	18.3	50.4	16.3	1.4

$$^b u = (W \times I_w) / I_u$$

of alkali-refined coconut oil (I.V. 7.2, S.E. 221.8) 200 g. of anhydrous methanol was added and the mixture refluxed for 2- to 2½ hours with 0.4 g. of KOH as a catalyst. After cooling to room temperature enough distilled water, acidulated with dilute HCl, was added. Esters were then extracted with ethyl ether, washed, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and finally distilled under vacuum.

Fractionation by decreasing solvent crystallisation method.—To 100 g. of methyl esters, taken in a 4 litre flask, 300 g. of urea and 2.3 litres of anhydrous methanol were added. The mixture was warmed on a water-bath and kept overnight at 29°, and the adduct was separated through a sintered glass funnel. The filtrate was then successively distilled and a series of fractions was collected. The adducts were decomposed by acidulated distilled water and the liberated methyl esters were extracted with ethyl ether, washed and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. First fraction was further resolved into three fractions so as to obtain smaller fractions for easier detection, To 31.68 g. of the first fraction (I.V. 2.9, S.E. 246.1) 94 g. of urea and 700 ml. of methanol were added. The solvent was successively distilled and fractions were collected. The weight of the esters were calculated on the basis of 41.92 g. The results of the fractionation are shown in Table I.

Fractionation by urea adducts elution method.—To 50 g. of methyl esters taken in a wide-mouthed flask 200 g. of urea and 300 ml. of methanol were added. The mixture was warmed and kept overnight. The adduct formed was filtered through the sintered glass funnel and esters were obtained from the raffinate as usual. To the adduct a known amount of alcohol (as shown in Table II) was added and the procedure repeated. The successive elution and collection of esters from the raffinate were conducted as shown in Table II. Finally the residual adduct was decomposed and esters recovered before.

D I S C U S S I O N

The iodine values of various fractions in Table I show how oleic acid has been distributed. It can be observed that unsaturation of the fractions continuously increases and tends to be maximum in the last fraction. Table II shows similar results but are reversed due to the nature of fractionation. The maximum I.V. of 52.1 in this fractionation, however, can be attributed to the efficient and selective method of fractionation.

An approximate composition of coconut oil fatty acids has been calculated and included in the tables. The separation of oleic acid from higher saturated acids, such as palmitic, has been effected as seen from the results. However, it seems difficult to resolve the mixture of oleic, myristic and lower saturated acids. The natural proportion of oleic acid in coconut

TABLE II
Methyl esters (50 g.) of coconut oil fatty acids (I.V. 6.9; S.E. 224) + 200 g. of urea + 300 ml. of methanol.

Fraction No.	Ml. of alcohol added, (Wg.)	% Yield of the fraction	I. V. (Iw)	S. E. (SEw)	Unsat. esters (u) ^b % fraction.	Sat. esters. % fraction.	% Sat. in ratio (sat/unsat).	Mol.	Approximate composition of saturated							
									C ₈ .	C ₁₀ .	C ₁₂ .	C ₁₄ .	C ₁₆ .	C ₁₈ .	C ₂₀ .	
1	300	0.78	52.1	200.4	0.48	61.53	0.30	38.47	1.3	0.09	0.21
2	275	0.36	39.0	200.6	0.16	44.44	0.20	55.56	2.2	0.01	0.19	...
3	100	1.89	3.78	204.2	0.27	14.23	1.62	85.71	8.7	...	0.50	1.12
4	100	2.39	4.78	205.3	0.29	12.30	2.10	87.70	10.4	...	0.87	1.23
5	100	2.94	5.88	208.4	0.29	9.87	2.65	90.13	12.8	...	1.55	1.10
6	75	2.40	4.80	208.5	0.19	7.92	2.21	92.08	16.2	...	1.38	0.83
7	75	2.02	4.04	216.1	0.23	11.38	1.79	88.62	10.5	...	1.48	0.31
8	75	2.35	4.70	217.0	2.23	9.78	2.12	90.22	12.3	...	1.88	0.24
9	75	2.01	4.02	217.0	0.24	11.94	1.77	88.06	10.0	...	1.50	0.27
10	75	2.51	5.02	217.2	0.26	10.36	2.25	89.64	11.5	...	2.05	0.20
11	75	2.33	4.66	219.4	0.21	9.01	2.12	90.99	13.3	...	0.03	2.09
12	75	2.08	4.16	220.2	0.19	9.13	1.89	90.87	13.0	...	0.09	1.80
13	75	2.06	4.12	222.4	0.16	7.77	1.90	92.23	15.3	...	0.33	1.57
14	75	2.18	4.36	222.5	0.15	6.88	2.03	93.12	17.4	...	0.37	1.66
15	75	2.07	4.14	222.6	0.14	6.76	1.93	93.24	17.7	...	0.37	1.56
16	100	2.78	5.56	221.9	0.22	7.91	2.56	92.09	16.0	...	0.76	2.02
17	100	2.83	5.66	221.3	0.11	3.89	2.72	96.11	31.8	...	0.55	2.17
18	100	2.79	5.58	224.3	0.14	5.02	2.65	94.98	24.0	...	0.79	1.86
19	100	2.64	5.28	235.7	0.06	2.27	2.86	97.73	51.7	...	1.92	0.66
20	100	2.66	5.32	256.8	0.03	1.13	2.63	98.87	96.4	...	1.40	1.23
21	Residue	3.53	7.06	256.8	0.03	0.85	3.50	99.15	128.2	...	1.87	1.63
Total ester					4.08		49.72				3.27	6.07	26.6	5.3	0.28	0.21
% Esters					8.16		87.44				6.5	16.1	53.2	10.6	0.6	0.40
% Acids					8.3						6.6	16.2	53.0	10.5	0.6	0.40

oil fatty acids is reported to be about 7 to 9%. The fractions No. 2 and 3 in Table I and fractions No. 11 to 16 in Table II, all of which are binary mixtures of C_{13} and C_{14} saturated acids, also contain 7 to 9% of unsaturated esters. The above observations are quite in agreement with the view of Schlenk⁶ that, there will be always an enrichment of C_{13} - C_{16} acids along with the unsaturated fractions of higher acids. The tendency to form the urea adduct may be estimated to be about equal for oleic and saturated C_{13} acid. The presence of oleic acid in those fractions to the same extent as in natural proportion may give the indication of equal tendency of oleic and C_{13} saturated acid in urea adduct formation. The considerable enrichment of oleic acid in fractions containing C_{10} and lower acids is due to the small tendency of these acids to bind with urea as shown by comparing the yields of complexes by Abu-Nasr, Potts and Holman⁶.

The compositions calculated from the urea fractionation techniques have been shown in Table III in comparison with those found by other workers⁷⁻¹⁰. Thus, the limitations of the urea adduct method do not allow the correct calculation of the composition of fatty acids lower than C_{12} . Cumulative percentages of these lower acids in both cases, however, can be seen to agree, including the losses in the experiments. Stearic acid, which is present to a small extent of 1-2%, has also not been detected. In the elucidation of the composition of fatty acids in coconut oil by fractional distillation of mixed acids or their esters, various workers have observed oleic acid to enrich with palmitic, stearic and linoleic acids and is found mostly in the last fractions and residues. Results of fractional distillation of fatty acids by Stokoe⁷, that of methyl esters by Armstrong, Allan and Moore⁸ and later of fatty acids and methyl esters in an improved column by Lepkovsky, Feskov and Evans¹⁰, showed that last few fractions and residue consisting of palmitic and stearic acids were also rich in oleic acid. Obvious cause of this is the small difference in boiling points of palmitic, stearic, oleic and linoleic acids.

TABLE III
Component fatty acids of coconut oil.

Acids.	Decreasing solvent crystallisation method.	Urea adducts elution method.	Stokoe ⁷ .	Armstrong, Allan and Moore ⁸ .	Collin and Hilditch.	Lepkovsky <i>et al</i> ¹⁰ .
Stearic	0.8	3.0	2.1	1.0
Palmitic	5.0	6.6	5.4	7.5	9.0	9.0
Myristic	18.3	16.2	17.5	18.5	17.5	18.0
Lauric	50.4	53.0	48.7	51.0	48.0	46.4
Capric	16.3	10.5	10.7	4.5	7.2	6.8
Caprylic	1.4	0.6	7.2	9.5	7.9	9.0
Caproic	...	0.4	0.2
Oleic	8.4	8.3	9.0	5.0	5.7	7.6
Linoleic	1.0	2.6	1.6

Thus, in the case of coconut oil fatty acids or their esters, urea adduct method fails to separate oleic acid from the saturated acids lower than C_{16} , but is efficient in separating oleic acid from higher saturated acids. Distillation efficiently separates oleic acid from the acids lower than C_{18} , but fails to separate oleic, palmitic, stearic and linoleic acids from one another. However, the efficiencies of distillation and urea precipitation supplement each other effectively in regard of the two variables. Distillation allows separation according to chain length so that in the fractions of a distilled product this factor cannot interfere any more with the urea separation according to unsaturation. In coconut and similar fats Hilditch¹¹ has suggested to esterify the whole of the mixed fatty acids and to separate all the lower saturated esters (up to those of C_{14} or C_{16}) by fractional distillation and then to hydrolyse the residual esters and apply the lead salt separation only to the remaining mixture of higher fatty acids. The lengthy procedure involving hydrolysis of the esters, lead salt separation, re-esterification and distillation can all be avoided if urea fractionation is directly applied to the ester residue after the distillation of esters up to C_{16} .

R E F E R E N C E S

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